

New ultra-cool stars and brown dwarf candidates in *Gaia* DR2

Céline Reylé¹

¹ Institut UTINAM, CNRS UMR6213, Univ. Bourgogne Franche-Comté, OSU THETA Franche-Comté-Bourgogne, Observatoire de Besançon, BP 1615, 25010 Besançon Cedex, France.

Abstract

The second *Gaia* data release (*Gaia* DR2) contains high-precision positions, parallaxes and proper motions for 1.3 billion sources. The resulting Hertzsprung-Russel diagram reveals fine structures throughout the mass range. This paper aims to investigate the content of *Gaia* DR2 at the low-mass end and to characterize ultra-cool and brown dwarfs. We first retrieved the sample of spectroscopically confirmed ultra-cool stars and brown dwarfs ($>M6$) in *Gaia* DR2. We used their locus in the precise Hertzsprung-Russel diagram to select new candidates and to investigate their properties. About 70% of the bright enough objects from the known sample are recovered, filling the gap with *Gaia* DR1. Furthermore, *Gaia* DR2 contains $\sim 100\,000$ $>M6$ and ~ 1000 L candidates (all are $\lesssim L5$). A tentative classification suggests that a few hundred of them are young or subdwarf candidates. Their distance distribution shows that the solar neighbourhood census is still not complete. *Gaia* DR2 offers a great wealth of information on low-mass objects. It provides a homogeneous and precise catalogue of candidates that is worthwhile to be further characterized with spectroscopic observations.

1 Introduction

The *Gaia* mission (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2016b) provides full-sky coverage down to the *Gaia* magnitude $G = 20$ ($V \approx 20-22$), at the spatial resolution of the HST, with about 70 observations per source over 5 years. Distances, with an amazing precision of 1% up to 2.5 kpc at the end of the mission, and proper motions are now measured for 1.3 billions stars.

As highlighted in the scientific demonstration paper from Gaia Collaboration et al. (2018a), *Gaia* astrometry and photometry are powerful tools for studying fine structures within the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram (HRD). It is now possible to distinguish the locus of different types of objects, as predicted by models.

The *Gaia* optical observations are not the most suitable observations for studying the low-mass reddest end of the HRD. Nevertheless, the large number of objects observed with an unprecedented precision, including trigonometric parallax, makes it an unrivalled data set for studying the ultra-cool and brown dwarfs.

Smart et al. (2017) compiled an input catalogue of known L and T dwarfs with an estimated *Gaia* magnitude $G < 20.3$, within the reach of *Gaia*. They identified part of them in *Gaia* DR1 (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2016a). They found 321 L and T dwarfs, with $10 \geq L7$, which corresponds to 45% of the brown dwarfs bright enough to be seen by *Gaia*. As they pointed out, this incompleteness is mainly due to the cuts made in the catalogue to ensure the quality of the data. With eight more months of observations, *Gaia* DR2 (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2018b) should provide more complete and precise data, and help to fill this gap. Recent discoveries show that even the local census is not complete as illustrated by the discovery of an L7 at 11 pc, close to the Galactic plane (Scholz & Bell 2018; Faherty et al. 2018).

In a first step, we search for known ultra-cool and brown dwarfs in *Gaia* DR2 and investigate their properties using

their *Gaia* observations (section 2). In a second step, we use the properties from the known sample to show the potential of *Gaia* DR2 to reveal new candidates (section 3). The conclusions and perspectives are given in section 4.

2 Known ultra-cool and brown dwarfs found in *Gaia* DR2

2.1 The sample

We considered these spectroscopically confirmed objects from the on-line census compiled by J. Gagné for M6 to M9 dwarfs¹ and brown dwarfs². We added objects from recent studies (Rajpurohit et al. 2014; Marocco et al. 2015; Robert et al. 2016; Faherty et al. 2016, 2018; Zhang et al. 2018). The numerous candidates found in photometric surveys without spectroscopic confirmation are not included.

We retrieved these entries using their 2MASS identifier and cross-matching of *Gaia* DR2 with the 2MASS catalogue (Skrutskie et al. 2006) provided in the *Gaia* archive (Marrese et al. 2017). We also used the *Gaia* DR2 identifier when available in the SIMBAD astronomical database (Wenger et al. 2000), particularly for the faint objects found from the SDSS (Eisenstein et al. 2011) and SIMPS (Artigau et al. 2009) catalogues that have no counterpart in 2MASS.

The resulting full sample includes 7821 ultra-cool dwarfs ($>M6$) and 681 L and T dwarfs, including 28 with spectral type $>L7$. Among them, 4173 $>M6$ dwarfs and 555 L and T dwarfs have a relative error on parallax $< 10\%$, full astrometric (coordinates, parallax, proper motions) and photometric (G , G_{BP} , G_{RP}) information (hereafter called sub-sample).

Fig. 1 shows the HRD of the full sample (gray dots), superimposed with the sub-sample. The color code gives the spectral type. The adopted spectral type is the mean of op-

¹<https://jgagneastro.wordpress.com/list-of-m6-m9-dwarfs/>

²<https://jgagneastro.wordpress.com/list-of-ultracool-dwarfs/>

tical and near infrared spectral type when both are available. We used $G-G_{RP}$ as a color index because these faint and red objects have a lower flux in the BP bandpass.

Figure 1: HRD of the known ultra-cool and brown dwarfs found in *Gaia* DR2. The color bar gives the spectral type range, where 10 stands for L0 and 20 for T0. The gray dots show the dwarfs having a relative error on the *Gaia* DR2 parallax larger than 10%.

As the sub-sample contains all astrometric properties, it allows us to explore the HRD as a function of transverse velocity. This is shown in fig. 2 where filled squares are objects listed as subdwarfs in the census, and open circles are objects listed as young candidates. Thanks to the high precision of *Gaia* measurements, it is possible to distinguish a sequence of young candidates (redder and brighter) with a low transverse velocity from the sequence of lower metallicity dwarfs (bluer and fainter). The vast majority of the subdwarfs have a high transverse velocity, indicating that they belong to the older populations of the Milky Way, as expected. This separation seems slightly enhanced in the G-J color index over the $G-G_{RP}$ index.

Figure 2: HRD of the known sub-sample found in *Gaia* DR2, in the *Gaia* (left) and 2MASS (right) photometric systems. The color bar gives the transverse velocity range. Filled squares are objects listed as subdwarfs in the census and open circles are objects listed as young candidates.

2.2 color and magnitude calibrations versus spectral type

Fig. 3 shows the M_G and G-J relations versus spectral type. We determined the relationships between M_G , M_J , G-J, and spectral type from a linear fitting of the sample:

$$M_G = 0.5 \times \text{SpT} + 11.2;$$

$$M_J = 0.38 \times \text{SpT} + 7.76;$$

$$G-J = 0.095 \times \text{SpT} + 3.77;$$

where SpT ranges from 6 (for M6) to 19 (for L9). While the G-J relation may be extrapolated for T dwarfs, M_G and M_J saturate beyond L9.

The gray dashed line in the right panel of figure 3 represents the relation derived from 304 L dwarfs found in *Gaia* DR1 (Smart et al. 2017). The difference is due to the evolution of the photometric system between *Gaia* DR1 and *Gaia* DR2, as described in *Gaia* Collaboration et al. (2018b).

Young candidates depart from these relationships, in particular in the M-dwarf regime. It is also possible to distinguish the relation followed by the subdwarfs. Such trends have been presented extensively in different photometric systems by Zhang et al. (2018) based on their sample of 20 L subdwarfs found in *Gaia* DR2.

Figure 3: M_G (left) and G-J (right) relations versus spectral type computed from the sub-sample of the known ultra-cool and brown dwarfs found in *Gaia* DR2. 10 stands for L0, and 20 for T0. The color bar gives the spectral type range, where 10 stands for L0 and 20 for T0. The squares show the subdwarfs and the open circles the young candidates. The black dashed line gives the linear fits. The gray dashed line is the relation derived from *Gaia* DR1 (Smart et al. 2017).

3 New ultra-cool and brown dwarf candidates in *Gaia* DR2

3.1 Data filtering

We chose to search for robust candidates by applying strong filters on *Gaia* DR2. In order to work on a precise HR diagram, we followed *Gaia* Collaboration et al. (2018a) to filter the data. We refer to this paper for a detailed description of the applied filters. Here we describe their effects only briefly. We retain objects with $\sigma_{M_G} < 0.22$ mag, $\sigma_G < 0.022$ mag, $\sigma_{G_{RP}} < 0.054$ mag, reliable five-parameter solutions (astrometric and photometric), and removed most artifacts.

The corresponding *Gaia* archive³ query is:

³<https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/>

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SELECT * FROM gaiadr2.gaiadr2_source
WHERE parallax_over_error > 10
AND phot_g_mean_flux_over_error>50
AND phot_rp_mean_flux_over_error>20
AND visibility_periods_used>8
AND astrometric_chi2_al/(astrometric_n_good_obs_al-5)<
1.44*greatest(1,exp(-0.4*(phot_g_mean_mag-19.5)))
    
```

Following Gaia Collaboration et al. (2018a), we also restricted the sample to low-extinction regions in the Milky Way and kept objects in regions with $E(B - V) < 0.015$ according to the 3D extinction map of Capitanio et al. (2017). The resulting fine HRD can be seen in Gaia Collaboration et al. (2018a)

3.2 Selecting new ultra-cool and brown dwarfs candidates

Fig. 4 focuses on *Gaia* DR2 HRD at the low-mass end, superimposed with the sample of spectroscopically confirmed ultra-cool and brown dwarfs found in *Gaia* DR2. Note that the HRD presents a population of stars on the upper right corner that we prefer to reject. Indeed they most probably are contaminated and show a suspicious color-excess (see Evans et al. 2018).

Figure 4: HRD of the filtered *Gaia* DR2 at the low-mass end, superimposed with the known, spectroscopic sample. Left: M_G versus $G - G_{RP}$. The color-code is function of spectral type and allows to define three regions, shown by the dashed lines: $>M6$, L, and T dwarfs. Right: M_G versus $G - J$. Squares are the known subdwarfs, open circles are the young candidates. The dashed lines aim to separate these different types.

We used the information on the spectral type to define separations in the HRD. They are shown by dashed lines on the left panel and suggest that *Gaia* DR2 contains 95142 $>M6$ candidates and 1009 L candidates (all are $\leq L5$). These indicative numbers exclude previously known objects in common that remained after we applied the filters described in the previous section (2566 $>M6$ and 220 L dwarfs).

We also used the peculiarities of the known sample to tentatively define regions where subdwarfs and young candidates are expected to be dominant. We used the $G - J$ color index as it better separates these types (right panel in figure 4), probably because of the larger wavelength extent between the G and J bands. The resulting HRD is shown on the right panel of figure 4, superimposed with the known subdwarfs (squares) and young candidates (open circles). Once again the dashed lines aim at defining approximate regions in the HRD where objects

are most probably young or subdwarfs. There are 351 new promising young candidates and 361 subdwarf candidates.

The retained candidates are reported in the M_G versus $G - G_{RP}$ plane in fig. 5 (left panel). Subdwarf candidates in particular lie in the same region as other candidates, and young, metal poor, or regular L dwarfs share the same locus. This is consistent with what is shown by the already known sample (right panel).

Very few are new young and subdwarf candidates (below the dashed straight line): 18, and 10, respectively. However we stress that these numbers are lower limits due to the successive cuts we made to the original *Gaia* DR2. In particular objects were rejected while cross-matching with 2MASS.

Figure 5: Left: retained candidates (dots) in the HRD. Squares are the subdwarf candidates, open circles are the young candidates. Right: retained candidates (dots) superimposed with the already known subdwarfs (squares) and young dwarfs (open circles).

3.3 Comparison with models

Evolutionary and atmosphere models of ultra-cool and brown dwarfs have been developed for a long time (see e.g. the twenty years old review from Burrows et al. 1998) and are successful today in reproducing color-magnitude diagrams in many photometric systems.

However, the strong added value of *Gaia* data in testing these models, that is, the precise parallax, will help refine these models. Here we show a preliminary comparison of our candidates with the new evolutionary models reported by Baraffe et al. (2015) that consistently couple interior structure calculations with the BT-Settl atmosphere models (Allard et al. 2013).

Fig. 6 shows the HRD of our candidates superimposed on these evolutionary models. They tend to confirm the locus of the objects as a function of the peculiarities we discussed in the previous section.

3.4 Completing the census

Fig. 7 shows the sky distribution of the known (top) and new candidates (bottom). The new candidates cover the whole sky, including the Galactic plane where we can expect more discoveries of hidden dwarfs, such as the newly characterized L-dwarf WISE J192512.78+070038.8 (Scholz & Bell 2018; Faherty et al. 2018).

Fig. 8 shows the distance distribution of previously known (pink) and additional *Gaia* DR2 candidates (blue) for L and

Figure 6: BT-Settl evolution tracks from right to left: 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, and 0.08 M_{\odot} at $[M/H]=0$, and 0.083 M_{\odot} at $[M/H]=-1$. Orange dots are new candidates, gray dots show the known sub-sample.

Figure 7: Sky distribution in equatorial coordinates of already known ultra-cool dwarfs having a counterpart in *Gaia* DR2 (top), and of all candidates found in *Gaia* DR2 (bottom). The dots are $>M6$, the blue open circles are L-dwarfs, and the red squares are T-dwarfs.

$>M6$ dwarfs. While several recent efforts (see Best et al. 2018a) have been made to complete the volume-limited sample of brown dwarfs up to 25 pc, *Gaia* shows that the census is not complete beyond 30 pc. The situation is even worse for $>M6$ dwarfs, which is not surprising since we here only considered the objects with spectroscopic confirmation. The ongoing and future spectroscopic large survey such as APOGEE

(Majewski et al. 2017), LAMOST (Cui et al. 2012), WEAVE (Dalton et al. 2014), and 4MOST (de Jong et al. 2016) will soon complete the census of sources that lie farther away.

Figure 8: Distance distribution of the L (left) and $>M6$ (right) dwarfs for the known sample (pink) and the candidates found in the filtered *Gaia* DR2 data (blue).

4 Conclusion

There are numerous late M ($\sim 100\,000$) and early L (~ 1000) candidates in *Gaia* DR2. The high precision of the HRD allows us to give an indication of some of the characteristics of the object, e.g. young or subdwarf. This rough classification was made to guide the target selection for follow-up, depending on the scientific case one may want to study.

The given number are of course indicative but they also prove that the census is not complete yet, even locally. Although we call them new candidates, some may be part of the significant number of ultra-cool and brown dwarf candidates found in large-scale surveys, and classified from photometry (e.g. Folkes et al. 2012; Smith et al. 2014, 2018; Schmidt et al. 2015; Skrzypek et al. 2016; Theissen et al. 2017; Best et al. 2018b). Still these numerous candidates are most valuable for follow-up since they benefit from the reliable *Gaia* observations, including precise parallax and proper motion.

Further exploitation of this data set will be useful for making a complete census of late-M and at least early-type brown dwarfs, refining their luminosity function, testing stellar and substellar models, and probing the old population in the Galaxy through the few hundred subdwarf candidates.

Gaia DR2 contains very many objects of the spectroscopically confirmed sample. However, *Gaia* DR2 is an intermediate release, on which strong filters were applied. Further releases will most probably continue to fill the gap.

The high precision of *Gaia* and the numerous candidates it provides with full 5D (astrometry and photometry) data, offers a great wealth of information at the low-mass end of the HRD. This homogeneous and precise catalogue is a worthwhile target to be further characterized with spectroscopic observations, and most likely has surprises in store for us.

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⁴<http://www.starlink.ac.uk/topcat/>

⁵<http://www.gnuplot.info/>